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Capacity Building and Employee Productivity: A Survey of Zenith Bank Plc Branches in Asaba and Abraka, Delta State, Nigeria

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Abstract

The study examined capacity building and employee productivity. The specific objectives of the study were to; ascertain the effect of talent development strategy and employee productivity, examine the effect of employee training on employee productivity, assess the effect of succession planning on employee productivity, and determine the effect of career counseling on employee productivity. Primary data was sourced through the administration of structured questionnaire to the employees of selected of Zenith Bank branches in Asaba and Abraka, Delta State. Secondary data was gotten through the review of related literature. The study adopted cross sectional research design method, which aid the researcher to collect quantitative data used to address the relationship between the dependent and independent variable. A total of 195 copies of questionnaire was administered adopting random sampling techniques, and 187 copies were properly filled and returned with was used for the study analysis. Data collected were analyzed using the Pearson's correlation co-efficient and hypothesis was tested using multiple regressions. The findings revealed that there is a significant effect between capacity building dimensions (talent development, employee training, succession planning and career counseling) and employee productivity. The study concluded that man capacity building strategies are key indicators to enhance employee productivity in the banking industry. The study recommended that banks and strategic managers in Nigeria should maintain and improve on their capacity building strategies which serve as the engine room in accelerating overall banks and employee productivity.

Keywords: Capacity Building, Organizational Performance, Employee Productivity, Succession Planning, career Counselling

Introduction

Capacity building involves targeted and strategic change choices to achieve desired results, focusing on successful organizational change and employee performance. Capacity building can be human resources or organisational systems focused, and subscribing to capacity building as a 'way of doing business' has various implications for any given organisation. Capacity levels are a general concern to both organisations and individuals as they define an entity's competitive advantage, giving it an edge against other players in similar operational contexts. An organisation's superior hand gained by offering superior value through its employees to its customers when compared to its competitors is defined as its competitive advantage, which can be achieved by providing or delivering superior quality in goods and services discharged into a given market at justified

pricing. The past decade has seen great growth in the capacity development concept in organisations, which emanates from change management strategies and lessons learned over time (Chrisoplos, Christie, Bergman & Hauer, 2019).

The concept of capacity development is evolving, including its definition, application, emerging assumptions, and consequences, and is being used in donor development projects (Rugumamu, 2018). ICT innovation is one of the aspects of capacity development capable of improving employee productivity, and organisations need to build up their human asset ability to survive present-day business challenges (Benjamin, 2018). Human capital is essential for scholarly capital creation, providing experience, mastery, instructive capabilities, and word-related skills (Illustrious & O'Donnell, 2017 and Wang & Chang, 2015).

Human asset development helps organisations enhance the capability of their employees by providing breakthrough information and anticipating the long-term learning limit (Torraco & Swanson, 2015). It also clarifies competency development in individuals and the arrangement of conditions to enable them to apply these abilities for their own advantage and the advantage of their organisation (Watkins, 2012 and Zahid, Sacreta, & Manisha, 2015). Human asset management is an integrated push to create human abilities to achieve an abnormal state of performance, and capacity building is an arrangement of practices identified with individuals' asset management (Gartner, 2015).

Employee productivity is the activity or procedure of playing out an errand or capacity, as well as how effectively it is performed. It involves the real yield or after-effects of an organization as estimated against its planned yields. Richard (2009) identified three territories of firm result: budgetary performance (benefits, return on resources, degree of profitability, and so forth), item advertise performance (deals, a piece of the pie, and so on), and investor return (added up to investor return, financial esteem included). Given that firms operate in a complicated and ever-changing corporate world (Okwuise, Ugherughe & Afunwa, 2017; Okwuise, Kifordu & Oghoghme, 2020; Okwuise, 2023), it is expected that organizations must strive to guarantee an aggressive edge, by planning a methodology that should be adopted if profitability levels must be upgraded (Marimuhu & Aokiasamy, 2019).

Depending of organizational climate (Okwuise & Ugherughe, 2023) the plans of most firms focus on investment in physical and material resources, neglecting human investment in capital and equipment. Organisations often fail to recognize the need for well-defined and sustained training and development for staff, leading to inappropriate, haphazard, or lopsided exercises premised on faulty diagnosis or organisational training needs. Management fails to consider staff members who have acquired additional skills and knowledge, leading to frustration and low morale.

As a result of this lackadaisical attitude of management towards training and development, there has been a progressive decline in the ability of manpower to cope with the challenges that arise from the unfolding of a new dispensation, the ceaseless glamour of social change, and social satisfaction in the banking sector. Along these lines, given the way that bank employees are relied upon to have a more extensive scope of aptitudes that upgrade and animate business exercises, which are basic for employee examination and task checking, even in the region of business exhortation, Basically, contemplates that elucidate our comprehension of capacity building on the employee productivity of banks is inadequate in Nigeria. Hence, this investigation endeavors to fill this imperative learning void.

Based on the research problems, the following questions were raised to guide the study: "What are the effects of talent development strategy on employee productivity?" "What effects does employee training have on employee productivity?" "How does succession planning affect employee productivity?" "What is the effect of career counseling on employee productivity?" Having seen the research questions upon which the research hypotheses of this study are built, the rest of the study is divided into four sections: the review of related

literature; the conceptual framework, theoretical framework, and empirical review; the methods and materials; the results and discussion; and the conclusion and recommendations.

Review of Related Literature

This section provides a conceptual, theoretical and empirical framework for the study, looking into the available streams of knowledge.

Concept of Capacity Building

Capacity building is a concept that is closely related to education, training and human resource development, but has evolved in recent years to cover both institutional and country specific initiatives (Williamson, et al, 2013 and Groot & Molen, 2010). UNDP (2017) defines capacity building as the process of enhancing capabilities in individuals, groups, institutions, organisations and societies to more effectively prepare for and respond to crisis or meet goals in a sustainable manner. Serrat (2009) and Lipson et al (2006) define capacity building as a process whereby people, organisations or society unleashes, strengthen, create, adapt and maintain capacity over time.

Capacity development for employees refers to improvements in the ability of all employees to perform appropriate tasks within a broader set of performance standards (Isimbabi, 2015 and Light, 2014). There are different approaches to capacity development, such as organizational, institutional, systems, and participatory (Rugumamu, 2011; Baser & Morgan, 2008; Eisenhardt & Martin, 2000). According to United Nations Committee of Experts on Public Administration (UNCEPA) (2016) capacity building takes place at three levels: individual, institutional, and societal. Institutional level capacity building involves modernizing existing institutions and supporting them in forming sound policies, organizational structures, and effective methods of management and revenue control, while societal level capacity building requires the establishment of an interactive public administration system that receives feedback from the population and makes public administrators more accountable and responsive (UNCEPA, 2016).

At the organizational level, Trott and Hartmann (2019) argue that capacity development can be in terms of process consultation, leadership development, promotion of networking and collaboration, action learning, advocacy and awareness creation, on the job training, technical advice, training course, and educational and continued professional development. The aim of the strategy is to achieve the desired goal. UNESCO (2015) capacity building is both a process and an outcome whose characteristics and principles are that: it's multidimensional, dynamic and continuous process linked to performance; it develops in stages and required at four levels - system/ institutional, organisation, personnel and community; it's planned and time bound intervention geared towards improving performance or meeting certain objectives; it's an internal process, which may be enhanced or accelerated by an outside entity to improve individual, organisation or institution's abilities; uses different and holistic approaches; involve all stakeholders depending on context and objectives; long term investment built on local capacity.

Conceptual Framework

INDEPENDENT VARIABLE

DEPENDENT VARIABLE

Source: Researchers Model (2023)

Theoretical Review

Theoretical framework is a set of relational words that explain why things depend on theories. Different authors have come up with theories on human capital development, such as performance and human capital development theory and dynamic capabilities and capacity building (David, 2009; Ofouma, Aniekwue, Edeme & Okotie, 2021).

Performance and Human Capital Development Theory

The theory of performance is useful for organisations and individuals to understand the process of performance, which includes context, skills levels, knowledge, identity, fixed factors, and personal factors (Caine et al, 2005). The Human Capital Development Theory argues that higher levels of missing capacity in a society are associated with greater levels of poverty. Emerging literature provides an entry point to measure the role of capacity in the development process (Baser & Morgan, 2008). Theories of Performance and Human Capital Development are used to scale up financial and staff resources and analyze capacity development strategies.

Dynamic Capabilities and Capacity Building Theory

Dynamic capabilities theory proposes a range of processes, resources and capabilities to enhance competitive advantage and drive innovation, capacity development and performance (Eisenhardt & Martin, 2000 and Anderson & Markides, 2006). Capacity development initiatives affect organisations and individuals through skills and knowledge, and individual learning contributes to organisational learning through policies, processes, information management and reward systems (Boesen & Therkildsen, 2004; Murphy & Hill, 2012; Palmer & Kaplan, 2014).

Mentorship, coaching, job capacity training, and innovation are keys to capacity development initiatives. Barreto (2010) argued that the value and performance of an organisation is measured by the level of intellectual and employee capacity, and that staff knowledge is important in cementing the capability of employees to make distinctions in the execution of their responsibilities.

Empirical Reviews

Ofuoma, Aniekwe, Edeme and Okotie (2021) examined the relationship between Human Capital Development and Organisational Performance in the Nigeria Aluminium Manufacturing Sector, using Whictech Aluminium Limited and Flight Aluminium Plc in Asaba, Delta State, Nigeria as the case study. Results revealed that there is a significant negative relationship between [Talent Development (TD), Training & Development (T&D), Knowledge Management (KM) and Career Development (CD)]. Investment profile of the studied organisations should be tied to human capital development elements, recruitment of experienced employees and creation of policies that encourages human capital development should be part of their strategic plans.

Nwankwo, Olabisi and Onwuchekwa (2021) examined the effect of capacity building on the organizational performance of multipurpose cooperatives in Osun central federal senatorial district of Osun state, Nigeria. Data was obtained from 529 management committee members across the study area and evidence revealed that capacity building activities were well established. To strengthen the capacity building in cooperative, re-orientation and sensitization of members and employees, integration and diversification of investment, and making cooperative extension services compulsory and accessible to all cooperatives are recommended.

Chukwurah, Uzor, Iwuno and Chukwueloka (2020) conducted a study on the level of low productivity among workers in the public sector. The study examined the extent to which capacity building enhances the quality of service delivery in the Anambra State civil service commission, Awka and identified the factors that have been militating against capacity building. The major findings were that lack of training, insufficient fund and lack of modern technologies are the major factors hindering capacity building.

Danjuma, Baba and Ashigar (2019) examined capacity building and increase efficiency of employees with the resulting increase in corporate productivity. There have been deliberate efforts by the government to encourage capacity building. One of these efforts was the establishment of Industrial Training Fund (ITF) with a view to ensuring that there is adequate manpower with the requisite skills in the country. However, the major problems facing capacity building and development have been that of low morale, insufficient information difficulty in the application of the concepts, and principles in real-life situations and non-evaluation of the outcome of capacity building. To enable effective capacity, Government should ensure effective enforcement of manpower policies as well as enhancing the confidence of its workers through capacity building. This, therefore, calls for continue increase in budgetary allocation to education, training civil servant so as to march skills and abilities to enhance effective performance and ensuring that performance is in line international standard.

Julius (2019) investigated the effect of succession planning on workforce productivity in Kenya. It found that most organizations are engaging in formalized succession planning to help high potential employees fit into management positions. Succession planning should include strategies that acknowledge the need and form of value generating skills and knowledge that the organisation would need, and transform these values to competitive advantage. It should also create corporate social identity for the organization, where employees see themselves as owners or partners together with the employer.

Mba, Aga and Onyia (2018) evaluated the effect of human capital development in organisational performance in manufacturing industries in South-East Nigeria. The sample size of 358 was determined using Ferund and William's formula and 306 copies of the questionnaire were returned and accurately filled. The validity of the instrument was tested using content analysis and the reliability was tested using the Pearson correlation coefficient (r). The hypotheses were analyzed using f-statistics (ANOVA) tool and the findings indicated that Knowledge has a positive significant effect on product quality and Skills have a positive significant relationship on promoting of innovations. Organisations should train their staff to acquire Knowledge to enhance productivity and market share. Provision of new technological equipment and training of workers on the machines should be encouraged for more profitability of the manufacturing companies.

Amir, Mohamad and Maryam (2016) examined the effect of succession planning on the performance evaluation based on the balance score card in Water and Sewage Company, the southeast Tehran. Results showed that succession directly affects the performance and has a positive and significant effect on the performance through the mediating variable of organisational commitment.

Otibine (2016) investigated the effects of capacity development strategies on performance of the Department for International Development (DFID) in Kenya. The findings showed that DFID capacity development strategies included effective financial management, human resource development and information management, communication and technology, and continuous automation of systems. These strategies contributed to timely fund flows, accurate financial forecasting, effective programme management, and enhanced relationships between employer and employees.

Edwin (2016) evaluated the effectiveness of capacity building in business development services (BDS) facilitating organisations in Kenya. A sample of 183 respondents was obtained using systematic and stratified random sampling techniques and the data was collected using self-administered semi structured questionnaire and analyzed using descriptive & inferential statistics. The results showed average capacity or performance in BDS organizations but with leadership, financial self-sufficiency and sustainability still performing poorly. Capacity building was moderately effective and accounted for 51.9% of organisation performance in Kenya. Future study should assess how deep capacity building affects organisation financial performance and effects of specific environmental factors.

Coffey (2015) examined the concept of capacity development through international projects. The study focused on the use of results based management (RBM) by donors alongside well-tailored monitoring and evaluation tools (including logical framework analysis, logic models and results frameworks). The study deduced that donor agencies relied upon such tools to generate the evidence base for measuring “success” across the spectrum of their work, although projects differed enormously in their nature, scope and time-span. Vallejo and When (2016), evaluated capacity development by identifying and analyzing the various approaches put forward over time. The study outlines the processes and challenges of CD when the pre-defined indicators are not captured in the preparation stage. The study indicates that CD strategy ought to consider the programme, human resources, beneficiary population, other stakeholders and the operational context and the lack of a tailor made approach to capacity development.

Yona, Rapheal and Eunice (2015) determined the effect of talent retention on employee’s performance, assess how talent attraction impacts, effect of learning and development on employees performance in beverage industry in Kenya. The study adopted a descriptive research design in which the target population of 2,500 employees of Del Monte Kenya. The study used stratified sampling method to select 83 employees according to their job cadres. Descriptive statistics such as the standard deviation, percentages and frequency distribution were used. The study established that the job retention motivated the employees of Del Monte leading to ultimate performance. The study recommended that the management should ensure the work environment was attractive to the employees so as to motivate, thus leading to better performance.

Gekonde, Nyamboga and Nyarohoo (2014) examined the influence of strategic human resource and organisational capacity building on performance improvement of public service delivery in the departments of the registration of persons in Nakuru County (Kenya). The study was prompted by reported incidents of low registration coverage in the issuance of Kenyan National Identification documents. The objectives of the study were to examine strategies put in place focusing on performance improvement, investigate on types of human resource capacity building advanced aiming at performance improvement, and establish challenges and possible remedies encountered by the human resource and relevant organizations. The study will be guided by the Roseau's psychological contract theory of (1994) which stresses mutual beliefs and expectations by employees

and organisations upon the successful performance of a worker. Descriptive survey research design method targeting 308 respondents and 9 sub counties will be used, with a sample size of 50%. Primary and secondary sources of data collection will be employed, and questionnaires will be used as data collection instruments. Data will be sorted out, coded and analyzed by using descriptive statistics and Statistical Packages for Social Scientists (SPSS). Multiple regression statistical models were used to test the advanced study hypothesis, which showed no significance relationship between strategies and performance improvement on public service delivery. Study findings will be subjected to review committee and open for public information and consumption.

METHODS AND MATERIALS

This section is concerned with providing the methods to be adopted in carrying out this study, which consists of the following: research design, population and sample size, sample techniques, instrument for data collection, validation of the instrument for data collection, method of data collection and technique of data analysis.

Research Design

The descriptive survey research is chosen because it is suitable for answering research questions relating to quantitative issues, who, what, when, where and how associated with a particular research problem. The descriptive survey research yielded rich data that lead to important recommendations in practices.

Population of the Study

The population of the study consisted of employee of Zenith Bank Plc currently operating in Asaba and Abraka, Delta State. The aggregate number of persons from which the study sample was drawn is estimated at 217 members, all of which are employees of Zenith Bank Plc in Asaba, Delta State. This is shown in table 1.

Table 1: Showing the Population of Collection of Zenith Bank Plc in Asaba and Abraka, Delta State.

S/N	Firm	Staff Strength	Percentage
1	Zenith Bank Plc (Nnebisi) (1)	71	18.6
2	Zenith Bank Plc (Okpanam) (2)	122	32
3	Zenith Bank Plc (Ezenei) (1)	57	14.9
4	Zenith Bank Plc (Abraka) (2)	131	34.4
Total		381	100

Source: Human Resource Department (2023)

Sample Size

For this study, the appropriate number of representation of the population for the study was determined using the sample size formula of Taro Yamani, thus:

$$n = \frac{N}{1 + N(e)^2}$$

Where n = sample size sought
e = level of significance

N = population size

Working reveals the desired sample size thus:

$$n = \frac{381}{1 + 381(0.05)^2}$$

$$n = \frac{381}{1 + 381(0.05)^2}$$

$$1 + 350 (0.0025)$$

$$n = \frac{381}{1+0.9525}$$

$$n = \frac{381}{1.9525} = 195$$

Sample size n = 195

To allocate the sample size of 195 to Zenith Bank Plc various branches in Asaba, (i.e. Nnebisi, Okpanam, and Ezenei) and the branch at Abraka, the study adopts the stratified sampling approach so as to give a fair representation to the selected banks. The Bowley’s proportional allocation formula is used. The formula states that in (Bowley, 1926) stratified sampling, the sample size for proportional allocation is given by:

$$n_h = n \frac{N_h}{N}$$

Where:

- n_h = Number of units allocated to each firm
- N_h = Number of employees in each firm stratum in the population
- n = Total sample
- N = The total population size under study

Zenith Bank Plc (Nnebisi)

$$n_h = \frac{195 * 71}{381} = 35$$

Zenith Bank Plc (Okpanam)

$$n_h = \frac{195 * 122}{381} = 64$$

Zenith Bank Plc (Ezenei)

$$n_h = \frac{195 * 57}{381} = 29$$

Zenith Bank Plc (Abraka)

$$n_h = \frac{195 * 131}{381} = 67$$

Table 2: Proportion of Sample Size from Each Branch

S/N	Bank/ N0	Sample Size
1	Zenith Bank Plc (Nnebisi) (1)	35
2	Zenith Bank Plc (Okpanam) (2)	64
3	Zenith Bank Plc (Ezenei) (1)	29
4	Zenith Bank Plc (Abraka) (2)	67
Total		195

Source: Survey Analysis (2023)

Sampling Techniques and Research Instrument

The sampling technique adopted in this study is the simple random technique.

Semi-structured questionnaire is the main instrument employed for data collection. The questionnaire is divided into two sections (A & B). The section A contains questions relating to the respondents` profile while the

section B concerns other questions on the constructs of capacity building and employee productivity. The questionnaire used consists of five (5) point likert-type questions ranging from a 1-Strongly Disagree to 5-Strongly Agree. It was suitable for this study because it is particularly suitable for measuring attitudes towards an object or for obtaining the response evaluation of an object.

Validation of the Research Instrument

i. Validity of the Research Instrument

Content validity was employed to ascertain whether the content of the questionnaire is appropriate and relevant to the study's objectives. To estimate the content validity, the study seeks the opinion of professionals on the field of management scientists in this area.

ii. Reliability of the Research Instrument

To establish the reliability of the instrument, a test-retest method was adopted. This entailed the collection of two sets of scores on two occasions. The instrument is administered to a group of staffs of the Zenith Bank Plc in Delta State (i.e. Asaba and Abraka) at interval of three (3) weeks. Thus, if the results from the test show some similarity, which can be established that the questionnaire is reliable.

Source of Data Collection

Data was obtained using a structured questionnaire (i.e. primary source). The questionnaire is self administered given to the employees of the bank under study. The questionnaire is divided into two segments; segment one concerning the bio data of respondents, segment two dealing with dimensions of capacity building and employee productivity.

Data Analysis Techniques

Data collected for the study was coded and tabulated. Statistical techniques of data analysis are applied in the study which includes descriptive statistics and regression analysis. The descriptive statistics include frequency distribution, measures of central tendency (mean) and measures of variation (standard deviation). The results were presented in tables. While inferential statistical technique was multiple regressions approach. It was used for the purpose of ascertaining the strength of relationship that exist among variables, determine to what extent the independent variable accounted for change on the dependent variable, as well as to test the statistical significance that exists among variable respectively. This ascertained using the statistical package for social sciences (SPSS).

Results and Discussion

This section deals with the analysis of data and the discussion of the results of the questionnaires administered to employees of Zenith Bank Plc branches in Asaba and Abraka, Delta State, Nigeria, to examine the effect of capacity building on employee productivity.

Analysis of Research Question One to Four of the selected Bank Branches

This section seeks to analyze each of the research questions and analyzed the responses of the respondents with descriptive statistics. The descriptive statistics which comprises of the minimum, maximum, mean and standard deviation was employed proper and thorough description of the independent variables (Measures of manpower capacity development) are; Talent Development (TD), Employee Training (ET), Succession Planning (SP) and Career Counseling (CC) and dependent variable {Employee productivity (EMP)} for this study, presented below:

Table 3: Descriptive Statistics

	N	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std. Deviation
TD	187	12	20	17.25	1.985
ET	187	12	20	16.27	2.213
SP	187	12	20	16.44	1.844
CC	187	11	20	16.50	1.933
EMP	187	11	20	16.64	1.927
Valid N (listwise)	187				

Source: SPSS Output, 2023.

The Table 3 above shows the descriptive statistics which comprises of the minimum, maximum, mean and standard deviation values of different variables used in this study. The independent variables used in the study which serve as the measures of capacity building, are: Talent Development (TD), Employee Training (ET), Succession Planning (SP) and Career Counseling (CC) and dependent variable {Employee Productivity (EMP)} were described using the descriptive statistics below:

The descriptive statistics for Talent Development (TD) indicate a mean of 17.25, a standard deviation of 1.985 with the difference in the maximum and minimum values which stood at 8. This implies that the variation in Talent Development (TD) is tremendous, since the mean value is greater than the standard deviation, by implications; the management of the bank under study take cognizance of talent development in their managerial plans.

Similarly, the descriptive statistics for the independent variable shows that Employee Training (ET) has minimum value of 12 and maximum value of 20 leading to the mean and standard deviation of 16.27 and 2.213 respectively. This implies that the Employee Training (ET) has been continues implemented in the banks and this is also reflected in the variation of the employee productivity, since the mean value of 16.27 is greater than the standard deviation of 2.213.

Also, the descriptive statistics for Succession Planning (SP) indicated a mean value of 16.44, a standard deviation of 1.844 with the difference in the maximum and minimum values which stood at 8. This implies that the Succession Planning (SP) varies tremendously and this is also reflected in the variation of the Employee Productivity (EP), since the mean value of 16.44 is greater than the standard deviation of 1.844.

More also, the descriptive statistics for Career Counseling (CC) indicates a mean of 16.50, a standard deviation of 1.933 with the difference in the maximum and minimum values which stood at 9. This implies that the variation in Career Counseling (CC) has increase, since the mean value is greater than the standard deviation.

Finally, the descriptive statistics for Employee productivity (EMP) indicate a mean of 16.64, a standard deviation of 1.927 with the difference in the maximum and minimum values which stood at 9. This implies that the Employee Productivity (EMP) varies aggressively over the years.

Correlation Matrix

Correlation analysis is used to examine the relationship between dependent and independent variables. Its values lie between -1 and +1. +1 indicates that there is a positive linear sense between two variables and are perfectly related while -1 indicates a negative linear sense between two variables. This tells the degree of correlation between the independent and dependent variables, whether there is moderate or low degree of correlation.

Table 4: Correlations

		EMP	TD	ET	SP	CC
Pearson Correlation	EMP	1.000				
	TD	.306	1.000			
	ET	.247	.438	1.000		
	SP	.317	.591	.528	1.000	
	CC	.574	.406	.300	.415	1.000

Source: SPSS Output, 2023.

The correlation matrix in table 4, showed the coefficient of the type of relationship that exist between the independent variables {Talent Development (TD), Employee Training (ET), Succession Planning (SP) and Career Counseling (CC)} and dependent variable {Employee productivity (EMP)}.

The Talent Development (TD) has a coefficient of ($r= 0.306 > 0.05$) which reveals that Talent Development (TD) has strong positive correlation with Employee Productivity (EMP), this implies that an increase in Talent Development (TD) would have positive effects on Employee productivity (EMP) of Zenith Bank Plc branches in Asaba and Abraka, Delta State.

The Employee Training (ET) has a coefficient of ($r= 0.247 > 0.05$) which reveals that Employee Training (ET) has strong positive correlation with Employee productivity (EMP), this implies that an increase in Employee Training (ET) would have positive effects on Employee productivity (EMP) of Zenith Bank Plc branches in Asaba and Abraka, Delta State.

Succession Planning (SP) has a coefficient of ($r= 0.317 > 0.05$) which reveals that Succession Planning (SP) has strong positive correlation with Employee productivity (EMP), this implies that an increase in Succession Planning (SP) would have positive effects on Employee productivity (EMP) in of Zenith Bank Plc branches in Asaba and Abraka, Delta State.

Career Counseling (CC) has a coefficient of ($r=0.574 > 0.05$) which reveals that Career Counseling (CC) has strong positive correlation with Employee Productivity (EMP), this implies that an increase in Career Counseling (CC) would have positive effects on Employee productivity (EMP) of Zenith Bank Plc branches in Asaba and Abraka, Delta State

The study is focused on enhancing employee productivity through manpower capacity development. The results of the correlation analysis involving all the indicators of manpower capacity development [Talent Development (TD), Employee Training (ET), Succession Planning (SP) and Career Counseling (CC)] reported positive correlation coefficient values among the measures. This indicated that they are appropriate dimensions of capacity building.

Table 5: Multiple Regression Analysis of Measures of Capacity Building and Employee Productivity Coefficients^a

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	2.970	.765		3.882	.002
	TD	.045	.021	.044	2.143	.013
	ET	.018	.037	.017	2.571	.005
	SP	.042	.021	.040	2.000	.016
	CC	.901	.140	.900	6.390	.001

a. Dependent Variable: EMP

Model Summary^b

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate	Durbin-Watson
1	.976 ^a	.953	.922	.941	1.021

a. Predictors: (Constant), CC, ET, TD, SP

b. Dependent Variable: EMP

ANOVA^a

Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	529.949	4	132.487	149.725	.000 ^b
	Residual	161.046	182	.885		
	Total	690.995	186			

a. Dependent Variable: EMP

b. Predictors: (Constant), CC, ET, TD, SP

Source: SPSS Output, 2023.

The results from the multiple regression analysis recorded the effect of capacity building on employee productivity of Zenith Bank Plc branches in Asaba and Abraka, Delta State. The four variables to measure capacity building are; Talent Development (TD), Employee Training (ET), Succession Planning (SP) and Career Counseling (CC) exhibited statistically significant positive effect on Employee productivity (EMP).

The result provided support for the H₁ test result which indicated that there is significant positive relationship between Talent Development (TD) and Employee productivity (EMP) ($\beta=0.044$; T-Value=2.143; $P=0.013<0.05$). The calculated p-value of 0.013 is significant because it is less than 0.05 (5%). It also means that the level of confidence (confidence interval) is 98.7% more than the acceptable level of 95%. We therefore, accept the alternate hypothesis and reject the null hypothesis (H₀₁), which states that there is no significant relationship between Talent Development (TD) and Employee productivity (EMP) of Zenith Bank Plc branches in Asaba and Abraka, Delta State. This implies that 1% increase in Talent Development (TD) would leads to 4.4% increase in Employee productivity (EMP), this is evident with a regression coefficient of 0.044. This finding is supported by the theory of performance views both organizations and individuals as a journey that goes though processes. It further portrayed that the process of performance comprise of context, skills levels, knowledge, identity, fixed factors and personal factors; human beings and organizations can produce extra ordinary performance based on their capacity levels of proper training. This is findings is supported by the empirical findings of Otibine, (2016) and Edwin, (2016).

Similarly the findings indicated that Employee Training (ET) is found to have significant positive relationship with Employee productivity (EMP) ($\beta=0.017$; T-Value=2.571; $P<0.005$). The findings provided support for the result of H₂ which showed that there is a significant positive relationship between Employee Training (ET) and Employee productivity (EMP) ($0.005<0.05$). The calculated p-value of 0.005 is significant because it is lesser than 0.05 (5%). It also means that the level of confidence (confidence interval) is 99.5% more than the acceptable level of 95%. We therefore, accept the alternate hypothesis and reject the null hypothesis (H₀₂), which states that there is a significant relationship between Employee Training (ET) and Employee productivity (EMP) of Zenith Bank Plc branches in Abraka and Abraka, Delta State. This implies that 1% increase in Employee Training (ET) would leads to 1.7% movement in Employee productivity (EMP) this is evident with a regression coefficient of 0.017. This finding is supported by the dynamic capabilities and capacity building theory opined that capacity development initiatives are key pillars in the learning by doing approaches. The effects of capacity development initiatives affect organisations and individuals through the skills and knowledge achieved, and emphasized through capacity building. Individual learning directly contributes to organisational learning through policies, processes, information management and reward systems based on the overall

objectives of the organisation. This is findings is supported by the empirical findings of Chukwurah, Uzor, Iwuno and Chukwueloka, (2020) Otibine, (2016) and Edwin (2016).

More also, Succession Planning (SP) has positive effect on Employee productivity (EMP) ($\beta = 0.040$; T-Value=2.000; $P < 0.016$). The calculated p-value of 0.016 is significant because it is less than 0.05 (5%). It also means that the level of confidence (confidence interval) is 98.4% more than the acceptable level of 95%. We therefore, accept the alternate hypothesis and reject the null hypothesis (H_{03}), which states that there is no significant relationship between Succession Planning (SP) and Employee productivity (EMP) of Zenith Bank Plc, Delta State, Nigeria. This implies that 1% increase in Succession Planning (SP) would leads to 4.0% increase in Employee productivity (EMP) this is evident with a regression coefficient of 0.040.

Finally, Career Counseling (CC) has positive effect on Employee productivity (EMP) ($\beta = 0.900$; T-Value=6.390; $P < 0.001$). This finding provides support for result H_4 test which indicated that Career Counseling (CC) has significant relationship with Employee productivity (EMP) ($0.001 < 0.05$). The calculated p-value of 0.001 is significant because it is less than 0.05(5%). It also means that the level of confidence (confidence interval) is 99.9% more than the acceptable level of 95%. We therefore, accept the alternate hypothesis and reject the null hypothesis (H_{04}), which states that there is no significant relationship between Career Counseling (CC) and Employee productivity (OP) of the selected banks in Delta State, specifically; Zenith Bank Plc, Asaba and Abraka, Delta State, Nigeria. This implies that 1% increase in Career Counseling (CC) would leads to 90.0% increase in this is evident with a regression coefficient of 0.900.

Also, the Table 4.4.1 which is model summary table show the correlation co-efficient (R) of the regression is 0.976 (98%) which indicates a very strong positive relationship between the dependent variable [Employee productivity (EMP)] of Zenith Bank Plc branches in Asaba and Abraka, Delta State, and the independent variables [Talent Development (TD), Employee Training (ET), Succession Planning (SP) and Career Counseling (CC)]. The co-efficient of determination (R^2) is 95% (0.953) showing that 95% of the variation in dependent variable [Employee productivity (EMP)] of the selected banks in Delta State, specifically; Zenith Bank Plc branches in Asaba and Abraka, has been explained by the independent variables [Talent Development (TD), Employee Training (ET), Succession Planning (SP) and Career Counseling (CC)] while the 5% remain unexplained in the model. With an R^2 value of 95% showed that the strong positive relationship is further confirmed. The adjusted R^2 measures the goodness or fit of the model. This shows the goodness of fit of the model and also explains the dependent variable in relation to the independent variables in 92 ways. The 8% left is known as the error term and other variables outside the model. From the above, there is conclusive evidence of serial or autocorrelation since the Durbin Watson calculated value of 1.021 is less than "2".

Lastly, the ANOVA Table 5 above, shows the overall significance of the significance of the model, has $F(149.725)$ with p-value is estimated at 0.000. This indicates that all the independent variables [Talent Development (TD), Employee Training (ET), Succession Planning (SP) and Career Counseling (CC)] jointly impact on the dependent variable [Employee productivity (EMP)] of Zenith Bank Plc, Asaba and Abraka, Delta State, showing that it is a sound model.

Conclusion and Recommendations

Conclusion

The study examined man power capacity development strategies on employee productivity, thus, it can concluded that, overall the manpower capacity development strategies had a positive significant effect on employee productivity of Zenith Bank Plc branches in Asaba and Abraka, Delta State, Nigeria. The study concludes the following:

Talent Development (TD) has significant positive effect on Employee productivity (EMP). Thus, management of banks should maintain and improved upon their talent nurturing as core objective, in order to continue to improve their performance. By implications, a well structure talent development framework will go along in accelerating the productivity of banks in Nigeria.

Employee Training (ET) has a significant positive relationship with Employee productivity (EMP). Based on the findings, it showed that integrating different employee training programmes has contributed immensely to continuous improvements of the banks and their overall productivity in Nigeria.

Succession Planning (SP) has a positive significant relationship with Employee productivity (EMP), thus the Nigeria bank should maintain and continue to improve up their succession planning, because it would go a long way in enhancing employee productivity.

Career Counseling (CC) has a significant positive relationship with Employee productivity (EMP). Based on the findings, it showed that counseling of employees with various relating to their career advancement and providing solutions to them by the banks has gone a long way in enhancing employee productivity.

Recommendations

The recommendations made flow from the findings of the study and constitute the study's advice to banks in Nigeria for improving their employee productivity. Based on the findings, the study recommends the following;

- i. Since, talent development has significant positive effect on employee productivity, thus, this study recommended that banks in Nigeria should maintain and improve upon their talent nurturing and management; this will go a long in enhancing their operational efficiency and overall employee productivity.
- ii. Also, employee training has a positive significant effect on employee productivity, thus, the study recommended that the banks in Nigeria should continue to maintain and improved employees capability and technical know-how via training and retraining, this would go a long way in enhancing their employee productivity.
- iii. Similarly, succession planning has a positive significant effect on employee productivity, thus, this study recommends that banks in Nigeria should maintain and improve on their succession planning management, this serve as engine room in accelerating overall banks employee productivity.
- iv. Finally, career counseling has a positive significant effect on employee productivity, thus, banks in Nigeria should set up career counseling units for their in each of their branches, this will go a long way in enhancing their employee productivity.

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